

IMPORTANCE OF SUGAR BEET (BETA VULGARIS) IN ENSURING FOOD SAFETY

Kuliboyev V.K., Mutalova M.K.

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Abstract. *In order to ensure food safety and meet the demand for sugar and sugar products, taking into account the ever-increasing population of our republic, to reduce the volume of imported (imported) sugar and to increase its production as much as possible, to create fruitful rows and varieties of sugar beet and scientific research is considered one of the urgent scientific problems.*

Keywords: *food security, sugar beet, high-yielding varieties, cluster method, sugar production, antioxidant.*

The main part. Food safety is one of the most urgent tasks facing the countries of the world. The UN is also saying today that it is time to completely change the approach to food production and distribution. After all, in an ideal situation, agriculture, forestry and fisheries are able to provide everyone with food and create a source of income for people, as in the brochure. Moreover, in such a case, agriculture will develop in the interests of people, and environmental protection measures will be implemented. It is known that agriculture is the leading sector of the economy in Uzbekistan. It employs 3.6 million people, i.e. 27% of all employed in the economy. The sector's share in GDP is 32%, while the land used in the sector occupies 45% of the territory of the republic. At present, more than 180 types of agricultural and food products are exported to more than 80 countries. Another noteworthy point is that the cluster method of production in agriculture has been introduced and is gaining popularity. This is confirmed by the fact that 62% of the agricultural land is covered by cotton and textiles, 8% by livestock and 7.5% by fruit and vegetable production. One of the priority areas of economic development is to supply natural, organic food products of our state of New Uzbekistan, which is one of the urgent problems facing the whole world today. It is known that the supply of raw materials for the existing factories of "Angren Sugar" LLC and "Khorazm Sugar" LLC in our Republic, as well as providing our population with sugar products, is one of the urgent issues. Providing a raw material base by creating industrial, disease-resistant varieties of sugar beet, reducing the amount of imported sugar, even a little, will serve to stabilize the economy. In particular, the selection of sugar beet varieties with a sugar content of 18-20 percent and a yield of not less than 450-500 centners per hectare, scientific justification and implementation of the cultivation of sugar beet suitable for local climatic conditions, genetically stable and resistant to diseases, is one of the main urgent issues. Drying of root crops leads to increased respiration, increased sugar loss and weakening of resistance to damage by microorganisms. increases 3 times for beets withered by 10% and 4 times for beets withered by 20%. Rotten beets have a 3-4 times stronger effect than those that have not lost their turgor. Sucrose is intensively decomposed, its chemical composition changes significantly (the amount of reducing agents, organic acids, polysaccharides increases).

Processing beets that are frozen and then thawed causes great difficulties. In some cases, the industrial production of sugar from such raw materials becomes impossible when the melted beets rot. In terms of nutritional value, sugar beet leaves are equal to the green mass of planted grass. 5 kg of leaves correspond to 0.9-1 nutrient units with a protein content of 110 g, with a yield of 25-30 t/ha, leaves provide about 2000 nutrient units.

At the same time, sugar beet tops contain oxalic acid salts, so feeding them to animals in

large quantities, fresh or ensiled, can cause calcium metabolism disorders and digestive disorders. Sugar beet has nutritional value compared to a number of crops. For example, the yield of green mass of corn on the cob is 30 t/ha or 7000 fodder. unit / ha, and sugar beet 30 t/ha root crops and 15 t/ha tops or 10500 fodder. unit / to.

	Raw	Cooked, boiled	Canned	Fresh juice
Water, g	87.58	87.06	90.96	-
Energy, kcal	43	44	31	30
Protein, g	1.61	1.68	0.91	1.02
Total fats, g	0.17	0.18	0.14	0
Carbohydrate, g	9.56	9.96	7.21	6.6
Fiber, g	2.8	2	1.8	0
Sugar, g	6.76	7.96	5.51	6.6
Calcium, mg	16	16	15	0
Iron, mg	0.8	0.79	1.82	0
Magnesium, mg	23	23	17	-
Phosphorus, mg	40	38	17	-
Potassium, mg	325	305	148	-
Sodium, mg	78	77	194	93
Zinc, mg	0.35	0.35	0.21	-
Vitamin C, mg	4.9	3.6	4.1	0
Thiamine, mg	0.031	0.027	0.01	-
Riboflavin, mg	0.04	0.04	0.04	-
Niacin, mg	0.334	0.331	0.157	-
Folate, mcg	109	80	30	-
Total phenolic content ^a	255	238	192	225
Total flavonoid content ^b	260	261	173	126

Waste from beet sugar production is defecating dirt (defect), which serves as industrial organic fertilizer. Chemical composition: 40-50% calcium carbonate (lime), 15% organic matter, 0.2-1.7% nitrogen, 0.2-0.9% P₂O₅, 0.5-0.9% K₂O. In fact, beets are classified as one of the ten plants with the highest antioxidant activity.

It is commonly consumed as a supplement in various food cultures as juice, powder, bread, gel, boiled, oven-dried, pickled, pureed, or jam. in table 1 as shown , 100 ml beetroot juice 95 Kcal energy , 22.6 g carbohydrates , 0.70 g proteins , 0.16 g total lipids , 0.91 g common diet fiber and 12 g total from sugar consists of Thus, the micronutrient composition of 100 ml of beetroot juice is 8.8 g sucrose, 0.86 g fructose and 2.5 g is estimated as glucose.

From the table apparently as it is sugar of beets in the composition very too a lot macro and micro elements there is this substances food safety in providing ta ' a person health for very too important was structural of parts consists of Sugar beet is among the crops that use water sparingly. It is second only to drought-resistant crops such as millet and maize in terms of moisture consumption per crop unit.

At the same time, the mass of organic matter grown in the process of sugar beet production is so great that the total moisture requirement of plants reaches 100 tons or more of water per ton of roots and tops. In terms of nutrient consumption, sugar beet ranks first among other field crops. Nitrogen - N (nitrogen dioxide NO_2), phosphorus - P (phosphorus oxide - P_2O_5) and potassium - K (potassium oxide K_2O) are especially important for him. In addition, the yield and sugar content of root crops can be negatively affected not only by deficiency, but also by violating the proportions of applied fertilizers.

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